

BED-MORPHOLOGY OF RIVER GANGA: A STUDY BETWEEN ANKIN GHAT AND KANPUR

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Abstract

Bed morphology is a Geomorphological subfield which analyses bed relief, bed materials, fluvial process and morphometry of bed topography. The main objective of this study is to analyze bed relief features particularly pools, riffles, ripples, bars and island in river Ganga between Ankin Ghat and Kanpur. This study also focuses light on the morphometrical analysis of river bed. This study is based on the field observation and field survey. The study region of river Ganga lies in lower part of the upper Ganga plain between two hydrological station Ankin Ghat (u/s) and Kanpur (d/s). It claims 188 km² river bed area and 81.50 km (reach length 60.75 km) thalweg length. The width of river course varies greatly from point to point as its maximum width is 5.02 km, while minimum is only 0.62 km. in 68 km channel length. River Ganga forms 21 pools, 20 riffles, 83 sand bars and 18 islands of vivid dimensions. Out of total river bed area about 46.71 % (85.93 km²) area is covered by sand bars, while 20.26 % (38.07 km²) area is covered by islands. Rest of the bed area (34.03 %) is covered by shoals, pools and riffles.

INTRODUCTION

'Channel bed' is a floor of river body where excessive amount of sediment may accumulate downstream or where erosion may take place depending on the channel slope and wetted perimeter. The floor, the land at the bottom of a body of river or any water bodies usually permanently covered by the water but possibly intermittently dried out. The bed morphology of river channel includes bed topography, and bed landforms. The erosional and depositional activities over the bed floor generate various geomorphic features ranges from the formation of riffle-pool to ripples and dunes. The bed materials, transport capacity and flow dynamics are important factor which determines the formation of bed landforms. A pool is characterized by a water surface profile less than the mean stream (channel) gradient and finer bed material, whereas a riffle has water surface slope steeper than the mean stream gradient and is composed of coarse bed material. Bars and Island are distinct landforms developed as positive landforms in river course by the depositional activities of river. Bars are elevated deposited landforms as being un-vegetated and submerged at bank-full stage. When bars become some stable vegetated and emerge only at bank-full stage converted as islands. The presence of channel banks gives rise to a class of large-scale bed form called bars, the dimensions of which are controlled by the flow width as well

as the depth. Ripple a series of small more or less parallel ridges, produced especially on sand by the wind and the current of a stream, or by waves on a shore.

The major objective of this study is to analyses and measure the dimension of bed landforms and to produced a holistic description of bed topography or River Ganga as a case study between two important hydrological station.

THE STUDY AREA

The study region is course area of river Ganga lies in lower part of the upper Ganga plain between two hydrological station Ankin Ghat (u/s) and Kanpur (d/s). The area under study extends from $26^{\circ} 27' N$ to $26^{\circ} 57' N$ latitudes and from $80^{\circ} 2' E$ to $80^{\circ} 23' E$ longitudes. It claims 188 sq km. channel course area. The actual length (channel length) of river is 68.00 km. long while the air length is only 60.75 km. long (Fig.-1). The width of river course also vary from maximum 5.02 km. in between village Radhan (on right bank in Kanpur Nagar district) and village Jajamau (on left bank of river in Unnao district), to minimum 0.62 km. in between Bandemata Ghat of Kanpur Nagar district and village Aurangabad of Unnao district. In the study region the river adopts a naturally dynamic, highly ruinous, meandering plan form. It becomes obvious that the area is a micro region in which the devastating displays of the holy Ganga are observed. River Ganga forms the boundary between Hardoi, Unnao and Kanpur districts. Kanpur metropolis is located at right bank of this river.

A sub continental and sub-tropical type of climate pervades over the study region. The average annual temperature of the study region is $25^{\circ} C$ with January ($7.75^{\circ} C$) being the coldest month and May and June being the hottest ($38.85^{\circ} C$) months. The average annual rainfall of the study region is 872.10 mm rainfall occurs mainly in monsoon months.

The sediments of river bed are mainly fine to very fine sands and looms. The island's soil characteristic is Typic Ustipsammments. In this region channel flows through sinuous, braided, meandering pattern and forms various sand bars, islands, pools, ripples, shoals etc. The islands of this channel are vegetated during winter and summers. Some of them are permanently vegetated and inhabited. Sand bars are also cultivated (growing vegetables) during dry seasons.

METHODOLOGY

The methodology of this study is inductive. The analytical approach is also applied to describe bed relief and their associated landforms. Various methods and techniques regarding the morphometrical analysis of river bed are applied. Relative relief is calculated by the Smith's relative relief method (1932); dissection index is calculated by the Dov Nir's method (1957); altimetric analysis is based on H. Bauling method (1935, 1939) and braiding index is computed by Friend & Sinha's method (1993). The survey of India toposheets on the scale of 1: 50,000 are used to obtain basic geomorphic

Figure 1: Study Area

information. The researchers have generated all essential field data with the help of survey instrument

1. Analysis of bed relief

Bed relief represents three dimensional features of the river bed between both the banks, which includes the measurements of area, volume and altitude of vertical dimension of bed landforms. There are various morphometrical methods to analyze relief character of river bed. This bed relief study includes the analysis of relative relief; absolute relief; dissection index; altimetric analysis etc. of river of bed Ganga between Ankin Ghat and Kanpur. The details of these analysis are as follows:

1.1 Relative relief

The relative relief of the Ganga river bed have been calculated by G. H. smith's method (1932) as follows:

$$\text{Relative relief} = \text{maximum height} - \text{minimum height}$$

Based on a grid square (1 km²).

According to this method the calculated value of relative relief are classified into four categories viz.; extremely low (0-4m), moderately low (4m-8m), low (8m-16m), and moderately high (>16m) and presented in table 1.

Table 1: Relative relief: Frequency distribution and spatial coverage.

Classes	Frequency (No. of grids)	% of the frequency	Cumulative frequency of percent.	Cumulative frequency.	Are in km ²	Area in %	Cumulative percentage of area.	Remarks
0-4	95	50.53	50.53	95	95	50.53	50.53	Extremely Low (R _{EL})
4-8	57	30.32	80.85	152	57	30.32	80.85	Moderately Low (R _{ML})
8-16	34	18.09	98.94	186	34	18.09	98.94	Low (R _L)
>16	2	1.06	100.00	188	2	1.06	100.00	Moderate High (R _{MH})
Total	188	100.00	-	-	188	100.00	-	-

Figure 2 and Table 1 shows that most of the area (95 km²) of river bed is characterized as extremely low relative relief (0-4m), which includes 50.53% area of total bed surface of the study region. The second important category of relative relief is moderately low (4m-8m), which cover an area of 57 km² (30.32% of total bed area). The low relative relief area (8m-16m) is observed in 18.09% of total bed area including the coverage of 34 km². Apart from these low relative relief categories only 1.06% of total bed area is covered under the higher relative relief category which is above to 16m (up to 18m) named as moderate high relative relief. The frequency polygon and bar-gram of relative relief

Figure 2

Figure 4

Fig.6

Fig.8

Figure 3

(Fig. 3) reveal a positive skewness which means that the maximum concentration of frequencies is in the extremely low relative relief category. The cumulative percentage frequency curve (Fig. 3) shows a steep slope up to moderately low relative relief (4-8m) category after which the slope of the curve becomes very gentle. The curve shows that closely hundred percent of the total area i.e. 98.94 %, lies within the first three categories of extremely low to low relative relief.

1.2 Absolute relief

The heights of the area above the sea level are considered as absolute relief. While determining the absolute relief of the area the degree of dissection is not taken into account. Such depiction of relief is useful in recognizing the former land surfaces. The contour map of the bed area helps in determining the absolute relief. The absolute relief is analyzed with the help of grid square which are drawn on bed surface map as one square is equal to one km². The detail result of absolute relief is mentioned in Table 2.

Table 2: Absolute reliefs: Frequency distribution and spatial coverage.

Classes	Frequency (No. of grids)	% of Frequency	Cumulative frequency	% of Cumulative frequency	Area in km ²	Area in %	Cumulative percentage of area	Remarks
109-110	2	1.07	2	1.07	2	1.07	01.07	Extremely Low (A_{EL})
110-115	64	34.04	66	35.11	64	34.04	35.11	Moderate Low (A_{ML})
115-120	79	42.02	145	77.13	79	42.02	77.13	Low (A_L)
120-125	43	22.87	188	100.00	43	22.87	100.00	Moderate High (A_{MH})
	188	-	-	-	188	100.00	-	-

Fig. 5

The range of absolute relief of the bed area in the study region starts from 109 m to 125 m. The aerial distribution of different absolute relief groups are shown in Fig-4. The lowermost relief (< 110m) is observed in small scattered patches which includes an area of only 2 km² (1.07% of the total bed area), while the lower relief group between (110m to 115m) covers nearly 34.04 % (64km²) of the total bed area. The major area coverage (79 km²) of bed surface is under the relief group of 115m to 120m which share 44.02 % of the total bed area of river. The high altitude relief category (120m to 125m) is observed in an area of 43 km² which covers the area of 22.87 % of the total bed area. The frequency polygon and bar-gram of absolute relief (Fig- 5) reveal a positive skewness which means that the maximum concentration of frequencies is in the low absolute relief category. The cumulative percentage frequency curve (Fig- 5) shows a steep slope up to low absolute relief (115-120m) category after which the slope of the curve becomes moderately gentle. The curve shows that closely hundred percent of the total area i.e. 76.06 %, lies within the second and third categories of Moderate low to low absolute relief.

1.3 Dissection index

Here dissection index is calculated on the basis of Dov Nir's (1957) suggested method. According to him "this method takes into account the dynamic potential state of the area-the ratio between relative altitude (the relief energy) and the perpendicular distance from the erosion base". His formula for calculation of dissection index is:

$$DI = R_r / A_r$$

Where DI stands for dissection index,

R_r stands for Relative Relief

A_r stands for absolute relief

Table 3: Dissection index: Frequency distribution and spatial coverage

Classes	Frequency (No. of grids)	% of frequency	Cumulative frequency	% of cumulative frequency	Area in km ²	Area in %	Cumulative percentage of area	Remarks
0.000-0.035	120	63.83	120	63.83	120	63.83	63.83	Extremely Low (D_{EL})
0.035-0.070	39	20.75	159	84.58	39	20.75	84.58	Moderate Low (D_{ML})
0.070-0.105	22	11.70	181	96.28	22	11.70	96.28	Low (D_L)
>0.105	7	3.72	188	100.00	7	3.72	100.00	Moderate High (D_{MH})
Total	188	100.00	-	-	188	100	-	-

The grid method is used for the computation of dissection index. The values of dissection vary between 0 and 1 and the value of ratio can never be more than 1 except in the case of vertical cliff, and similarly 0 value is possible only in theoretical framework.

The calculated dissection index values calculated are classified into four categories such as: extremely low (0 to 0.035), moderate low (0.035 to 0.070), low (0.070 to 0.105), and moderate high (>0.105) (Table 3). These categories are shown in Fig. 6. The spatial pattern of dissection index analysis shows that the extremely low category (0.000 to 0.035) of dissection index covers 63.83 percent (120 km²) of area. The moderate dissection index category (0.035 to 0.070) accounts for only 20.75 % or 39 km² of total area whereas the low (0.070 to 0.15), and moderate high (>0.105). Categories of dissection index cover 11.70 % (22 km²) and 3.72 % (7 km²) of the total area of the study region respectively (table 3). The bed morphological pattern shows that 96.28 % or closely 100 % of the area of the Ganga river basin is very little dissected. The frequency polygon and bar-gram of dissection index (Fig. 7) reveal a negative skewness which means that the maximum concentration of frequencies is in the extremely low dissection index category.

Fig. 7

1.4 Altimetric analysis

H. Bauling (1935, 1939) has proposed a grid method. According to him the region to be studied should be divided into as many grid squares as possible and the highest point of each grid should be tabulated into several height-groups at increasing class-intervals. In the case of normal erosional landforms, the plotting of the highest points of the grid square would form frequency maxima at the same elevation, whereas the frequency distribution histogram of a region having some deformation would produce frequency maxima at different levels. The size of the grid depends upon the texture of the terrain. A large total of observations would provide good results; therefore, a close grid is necessary for a heavily dissected terrain.

The grid method has been used for altimetric analysis in the present study. The area has been covered with the grid squares of one km² having 188 grids. The highest point of each grid has been tabulated into three class-intervals of 2m, 4m, 6m, and the frequency of the highest points have been plotted on the horizontal axis against the corresponding height groups on the vertical axis. The selection of the highest point in the grid square, on the basis of highest contour of the grid, because there is no spot-height No. in the river bed. The observed highest point of different class-group are mentioned in table 4 and altimetric frequency histogram and curve are shown in Fig. 8.

Table 4: Altimetric analyses in the study region

Class interval (height in metres)	Highest point (Class interval in 2 m.)	Highest point (Class interval in 4 m.)	Highest point (Class interval in 6 m.)
110-112	2	22	57
112-114	2		
114-116	20	47	
116-118	35		82
118-120	12	70	
120-122	40		
122-124	21	25	37
124-126	4		
126-128	12	17	
128-130	5		12
130-132	5	7	
132-134	2		
Total	188	188	188

2. Landforms formed in River Bed

Various landforms have been developed over the bed surface either by the erosional or depositional activities in the bed of river Ganga under the study region. The bed topography of river channel refers to configuration of the river beds in terms of positive and negative features e.g. presence or absence of riffles and pools, sand bars and sand islands, shoals, sand dunes etc. Such depositional and erosional features (pools) developed in channel beds are the result of interactions of channel flow and transport of sediment load both as suspended sediment load and bed-material load. The important land forms are discussed here as below:

2.1 Pools and riffles

Pools and riffle is a pattern developed in the bed of a stream by a sequence of alternating scoured pools and shallow gravel bars termed riffles, even if the channel is straight and the bed uniform. Pools and riffles are prominent topography in the bed surface of river Ganga. During the study through the intensive survey of river bed, 21 pools and 20 riffles are observed of different shapes and sizes. In our study region most of the pools and riffles are developed in sinuous course and the frequency are higher in the low spacing. As figer-9 shows that the mean width of pools ranges between 275.0 m. to 86.0 m., while the mean depth varies from 1.70 m. to 1.65 m. The lengths of pools are measured from 5.65 km. to 0.30 km. The mean width of riffles varies from 351.0 m. to 091.0m., where as the mean depth of riffles ranges between 0.87 m. to 0.65 m. The length of riffles are also varies greatly between 5.15 km. to 0.50 km.

2.2 Sand bars

In post-monsoon period the velocity and discharge of river water decreases gradually and bars formation become common phenomena on the bed surface throughout the river bed (Fig. 9). The bars are formed of various size and shape during the dry season. About 65.95% of total river bed area is covered by 83 bars and 18 islands. In this coverage only bars contribute 45.69%of the total bed area. Due to the presence of bars and island water of the river flows through very narrow and irregular channel. Due to shape and location of bars, these are classified into various groups. Alternate bars or parts of them have also been referred to as unit bars, longitudinal bars, side bars, transverse bars, cross-channel bars, and diagonal bars and riffles. The channel side's bars are observed in scattered form and distributed from upstream to down stream of the Ganga channel (Fig. 10). In our study region about 18 side bars are observed of various sizes, the maximum length of sand bar's are 9.25 km.while maximum width 3.60 km. maximum area is 7.925 km. maximum height is 121.65 m. in different localities. One side bar is found along the left bank in upstream of the channel near Lukaia Purwa, Gahur Purwa, Bhagwant purwa, and Rataipurwa village. This bar is 8.10 km. long and its maximum width is 0.75 km. (4.375 km² area), other side bars of upstream bed are located near Akbar pur Sang in right bank and near Chaugawan village in left bank. The major concentration of side bars are in middle section of channel bed where

two bars are large size and rest three are of small sizes. In down stream channel bed 5 small but long and narrow side bars are observed in scattered form. Channel junction bars are formed at three localities one in upstream where river Isan join the Ganga and bars are formed around the Gaury Katery Island. Rest two junction bars are formed in middle lower stream at the junction of river Kalyani and Non Nadi respectively these bars are very small in size and narrow in shape.

Mid-channel bars are formed almost in all major section of river, but mainly it is observed in upper-middle section near the Radhan village, where more than one dozen bars of different sizes are located. In other section this type of bars are observed occasionally. The diamond bars are also formed mostly in upper-middle section near village Rustampur, Parshadipur & near Durgapur Tar Ghat (left bank) and Pahcham Purwa & Piaripun village (right bank). The points bars are formed along the meander near village Parshadipur, Aurangabad and Debi Purwa (left bank side) where the bars are very long and narrow in shape. Some bars are formed as island tell-deposits which are called here tell bars. Such tell bars are observed mainly in upper upstream and lower down-stream. Such bars are formed along the south-eastern Gauri Katri island (no-I₁) and others are along the south-east of the island no -5, south-east of the island No.-12, south-west of island No-17 and east of island no-18 (Fig. 10). In middle section of channel three and in lower section one rectangular bar are observed. Besides these bars two triangle bars are also observed in middle section of river channel.

Fig. 9

Fig. 10

2.3 Islands

When bars become some stable vegetated and emerge only at bank-full stage converted as islands. Thus, it is difficult to assess when a bar becomes an island. Furthermore, such a distinction between bars and islands artificially separates depositional forms that may have a common geometry and genesis. It is much more desirable to distinguish single braid bars from multiple bars (bar assemblages or floodplain segments) that are bounded by main channels. In our study area such geomorphic phenomenon has been observed at various sites in river course. In this study region three types of islands such as split, occasional and frequent are formed. Almost all the islands are vegetated and cultivated during the whole dry season. Gauri Kateri Island is larger in size and permanently inhabited. The area of this island is 9.47 km², while its minimum length and width are 5.75 km and 2.25 km its maximum height is 123.25m., from mean sea level. The other island area ranges from 9.475km² to 0.045km. and their length and width varies from 5.75km to 0.60 km and 3.75km to 0.28 km (Fig. 10).

2.4 Ripple

A bed form is defined as a single geometrical element, such as a ripple or a dune. Ripples form at the threshold of bed-load motion if the flow is hydraulically smooth and sub-critical. In hydraulically smooth flows, individual bed grains lie within the viscous sub-layer. Under these threshold hydraulic conditions, mean bed-grain size must be less than about 0.7 m. m. thus, ripples are effectively restricted to very-fine to medium sands, and some coarse sand. Ripples do not occur in mud, because such fine-grained sediment is suspended as soon as it is entrained from the bed. However, ripples can form if the mud is in the form of sand-sized pellets that are transported as bed-load. Ripples are less than 0.6 m. long and less than 0.04 m. high. Ripples are temporary landforms which are formed when water discharge and velocity decreases up to a very high level and observed over the bars when bars become dry. Such bed forms are observed throughout the study region and shifted from lateral side to the water current side and vanished due to wind erosion during the dry summers.

CONCLUSION

Bed geomorphology refers to bed relief, which represents three dimensional features of the river bed between both the banks, which includes the measurements of area, volume and altitude of vertical dimension of bed landforms. This study focuses light on the various parameters of bed relief of river Ganga which includes the analysis of relative relief; absolute relief; dissection index; altimetric analysis etc. as well as bed land forms developed between Ankin Ghat and Kanpur. Most of the area (95 km²) of river bed is characterized as extremely low relative relief (0-4 m.), which includes 50.53% area of total bed surface of the study region. The heights of the area above the sea level are considered as absolute relief. The major area coverage (79 km²) of bed surface is under the relief group of 115 m. to 120 m. which share 44.02% of the total bed area of river. The spatial pattern of dissection index analysis shows that the extremely

low category (0.000 to 0.035) of dissection index covers 63.83 percent (120 km²) of area. Categories of dissection index cover 11.70% (22 km²) and 3.72% (7 km²) of the total area of the study region respectively. The bed morphological pattern shows that 96.28% or closely 100% of the area of the Ganga river basin is very little dissected. During the intensive survey of river bed, a large number of bed landforms such as 21 pools, 20 riffles 83 bars, 18 islands and numerous ripples are observed of different shape and sizes. It shows that the bed topography of river Ganga between Ankin Ghat and Kanpur is not uniform through out the bed and the landforms developed over the bed are very irregular.

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